

FAILURE ANALYSIS OF WOVEN FABRIC CURVED LAMINATE WITH VARIABLE THICKNESS

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Abstract

In order to discover the failure features and failure mechanism of the curved woven fabric laminates subjected to eccentric static loads, four kinds of curved composite specimens with different thickness and different stacking sequence are investigated both experimentally and numerically. Experimentally, four different batches of specimens are quasi-static tested using the MTS material testing machine. The failure modes, failure locations, phenomena during the testing process, and the load-displacement curves of each kinds of specimens are discussed in detail. Through the experimental results, it is found that, firstly, the failure mode of all the specimens is delamination; secondly, the failure location is close to the inner surface of the curved laminate; thirdly, the curved woven fabric laminates fail unstably and the delamination instantaneously develops to quite long area inside the specified layer after its initiates. Numerically, three-dimensional finite element analyses are conducted to obtain the stress distribution along the circumferential direction and radial direction in the curved region. Through the analysis of the simulation results, it is found that the radial stress contribute the most to the delamination and the radial stress is high between the layers with different stacking angles.

1 Introduction

High specific stiffness and strength are being supplemented with the requirement for high toughness and efficient manufacturability in the aerospace performance criteria, thus the woven fabric laminates are becoming more widely used in many structures. In addition, curved laminate is a very common generic structural component in many aviation applications. The final failure mode in such structures is usually found to be delamination due to the high and discontinuous interlaminar stress between adjacent plies and the low strength in through-the-thickness direction. It is difficult for

designers to design a more reliable configuration against the delamination failure with little available interlaminar tensile strength data. The most probably load condition for curved laminate is bending. A better understanding of the stress distribution and failure mechanism of such kind of structures subjected to bending load is important and necessary. Many works have been done to study the failure of curved laminate. For example, a closed form solution for the elasticity of the curved laminate under pure bending and shearing loads has been provided by Lekhnitskii[1]. K. Lin and C. Hsieh[2,3] have constructed the mathematical expressions for the curved laminate with different curvatures under axial load, shearing load, radial load and tangential load, and the coincidence of the results between using the analytical method and numerical method is good, but the failure location and mechanism cannot be obtained according to their method. W. Cui [4] et al., referring to ASTM D6415 test standard [5], have proposed a measurement of interlaminar tensile strength using four-point curved beam specimens and achieved the interlaminar tensile strength values. However, their test configuration is not the same as the real load condition.

Much of the previous studies were focused on the basic performance of the curved laminate, while, the actual load bearing conditions in the real structures are usually simplified or neglected. In the NASA Langley Research Center, R. Martin et al [6-7] have studied the delamination failure in unidirectional and cross-ply curved composite laminate experimentally and numerically, but they simplified the load condition and the prediction of the failure is conservative. Joh [8] has measured the strain distribution of the curved laminate under load using the Moire interferometry whole-field optical method, but the accuracy of this method is needed to be increased to predict the real stress distribution in the curved region along the thickness direction.

Most of these studies are based on the laminates made of unidirectional lamina, and the researches on curved laminate made of woven fabric are rarely seen in the previous work. The present paper proposed an experimental and numerical study on the failure of woven fabric composite curved laminate with variable thickness subjected to bending loads. The simulation model was created by using ABAQUS software and USDFLD subroutine considering the progressive failure process and stiffness reduction of composite material. Both the stress distribution and the failure process were simulated and studied.

2 Experimental studies

2.1 Specimens description

To investigate the influence of the thickness and stacking sequence on the mechanical behaviors of the woven fabric curved laminate, four different types of specimens are tested in this research. The geometry and dimensions of the specimens are shown in Fig.1, in which the locations and dimensions tolerances conform to the general tolerance requirements for composite products HB 7741-2004. The four different kinds of specimens all have 40 mm long arm, 150 mm long leg, and 50 mm width. The inner radius is 5 mm.

Fig. 1 Geometry and dimensions of the specimen
The cured laminates are made of Cytec carbon fiber/epoxy woven fabric, whose nominal cured ply thickness is 0.216 mm.

The differences between the four different kinds of specimens are the ply numbers and stacking sequence, which are shown in Table 1 in detail.

Table 1 Specimen configurations

Specimen No.	Stacking sequence
Fabric-1	$[(\pm 45)/(0,90)/(\pm 45)_3]_s$
Fabric-2	$[(\pm 45)/(0,90)/(\pm 45)_4]_s$
Fabric-3	$[(\pm 45)/(\pm 45)/(0,90)/(\pm 45)_4]_s$
Fabric-4	$[(\pm 45)/(0,90)/(\pm 45)/(0,90)/(\pm 45)_4]_s$

The “(angle value)”, such as “ (± 45) ”, indicates the woven fabric with its warp direction shifting 45° from the 0° direction shown in Fig.1.

The direction of the ply with 0° stacking angle is coincident with the longitude direction of the curved laminate, which means the “L” and “T” direction of the woven fabric lamina with 0 degree ply are coincident with the “0” and “90” directions of the coordinate system shown in Fig.1, respectively, and the “Z” direction of the woven fabric lamina is the thickness direction of the curved laminate plate.

The “L”, “T” and “Z” directions are the warp, weft, and thickness directions of the woven fabric lamina, respectively.

The mechanical properties of the woven fabric are as follows: $E_L=56.1$ GPa, $E_T=60.6$ GPa, $E_Z=10$ GPa, $G_{LT}=3.46$ GPa, $G_{LZ}=G_{TZ}=5.24$ GPa, $\nu_{LT}=0.042$, $\nu_{LZ}=\nu_{TZ}=0.32$, $S_L^T=668$ MPa, $S_L^C=754$ MPa, $S_T^T=S_T^C=706$ MPa, $S_Z^T=S_Z^C=48.5$ MPa, $S_{LT}=112$ MPa, $S_{TZ}=S_{LZ}=115$ MPa. The superscripts T and C indicate tension and compression, and the subscripts “L”, “T” and “Z” indicate are the warp, weft and thickness directions of the woven fabric lamina.

The four strain gauges shown in Fig.1 are used to measure the strain values and to adjust the alignment.

2.2 Test setup

Four batches of specimens (six in each batch) with the configurations described in last section are quasi-tensile tested by using a MTS electron-hydraulic servo-controlled material testing machine as shown in Fig.2. Fig.2 (a) illustrates the specimen installation method on the material testing machine, and Fig.2(b) illustrates the specimen modification method to connect to the testing machine. The end of the curved laminate leg is clamped by the stationary head the testing machine, and the grip length is 20mm. To connect the curved laminate together with the movable head of the testing machine, two holes with 6 mm diameter are drilled on the arm of the specimen, and the distance between the center line of the holes and the curved region of the specimen is 20mm. The arm of curved laminate is connected with the “rigid” jig through two sets of M5 bolts, and the jig is clamped together

with the movable head of the testing machine. The quasi-static tensile tests are performed in displacement control mode at a constant speed of 1 mm/min via the moving head. The tests will terminate as the joint cannot take any further load. The circumstance temperature was kept being 23+/- 5°C, and the relative humidity was kept being 55+/- 5% during test.

(a) Specimen installation

(b) Connection holes on specimens

Fig. 2 Test setup

The lateral faces of the specimens are pasted with white correction fluid or red paint for better detection of the failures.

2.3 Test results analysis

1) Test phenomena

There are large deformations on all the specimens during the testing process. There is no obvious audible voice before the final failure, and there are very high voice emitted when the specimens are delaminated. The failure modes of all the specimens

are delamination at the location of the curved angle, and the delamination will extend to all over the 90° curved angle instantaneously after the delamination initiates.

The typical failure modes and locations of the four different kinds of specimens are shown in Fig.3. From Fig.3, it can be seen that the failure modes of the specimens are all delamination. However, the locations of the delamination along the thickness direction are different for the different kinds of specimens. Both the delamination of the Fabric-1 and Fabric-4 locate near the inner surface of the curved laminates. Whereas, there are two different delamination locations on Fabric-2 and Fabric-3. One delamination is close to the inner surface and the other is about in the middle of the curved laminate in thickness direction, and the latter one is much longer than the former one.

(a) Fabric-1

(b) Fabric-2

(c) Fabric-3

(d) Fabric-4

Fig.3 Failure modes of the specimens

2) Load-displacement curves

The typical load-displacement curves of the four different kinds of specimens are shown in Fig.4. From Fig.4, it can be seen that the stiffness of the curved laminates increases with the increase of the thickness of the curved laminate. However, the load capacities (maximum load value) of curved laminate do not follow the same rules. The specimen of Fabric-2 shown in Table 1 has the maximum load capacity among the four different kinds of specimens, and the load capacity of the Fabric-4, which is the thickest specimen, is lower than those of the Fabric-2 and Fabric-3. Both the load capacity and stiffness of Fabric-1 are the lowest.

From Fig.4, it can also be seen that the test loads of all of the specimens drop down abruptly without any advanced signs such as stiffness decreasing.

Fig.4 The load-displacement curves of the four different kinds of specimens

3 Numerical study

To simulate the testing process, three-dimensional finite element analysis are conducted using commercial finite element code Abaqus, and the 3D FE model of the Fabric-1 specimen is shown in Fig.5.

Because of the symmetric features of the structure, ply sequence, and boundary conditions with respect to XY plane shown in Fig.1, half of the joint is modeled to shorten the computing time, therefore, the curved laminate is modeled to be 25 mm wide. The leg of the curved laminate is modeled to be 80 mm long since the clamping length of the leg is 20 mm. Because the stiffness of the jig is much higher than that of the specimen, thus the jig is treated as rigid body and modeled as a reference point to decrease the contact pairs between the jig and the bolts. Contact algorithm is used to define the interactive relationship between the fastener and specimen.

In Abaqus software, the hexahedral elements use either “full” or “reduced” integration to allow complete generality in material behavior. For full integration the number of integration points is sufficient to integrate the virtual work expression exactly, at least for linear material behavior. Most fully integrated solid elements are unsuitable for the analysis of (approximately) incompressible material behavior because the material behavior forces the material to deform (approximately) without volume changes. For reduced integration the number of integration points is sufficient to integrate exactly the contributions of the strain field that are one order less than the order of interpolation. Comparing with the full integration, the advantage of the reduced integration elements is that the strains and stresses are calculated at the locations that provide optimal accuracy, the so-called Barlow points. A second advantage is that the reduced number of integration points decreases CPU time and storage requirements. However, the disadvantage of the reduced integration elements is that the reduced integration procedure can admit deformation modes that cause no straining at the integration points. These zero-energy modes make the element rank-deficient and cause a phenomenon called “hourglassing,” where the zero energy mode starts propagating through the mesh, leading to inaccurate solutions. This problem is particularly severe in first-order quadrilaterals and hexahedra[9]. To prevent these excessive deformations, an additional artificial stiffness is added to the element. In this so-called hourglass control procedure, a small artificial stiffness is

associated with the zero-energy deformation modes. Therefore, to avoid shear locking problem, to simulate the bending deformation introduced by the secondary bending effect more accurately, and to decrease the computing time, the enhanced hourglass control and reduced integration linear eight-node brick elements, C3D8R, are used to model each ply of the laminate and the fasteners of the model. The curved laminate is modeled as 31290 elements and 36060 nodes, and the fastener is modeled as 10808 elements and 12605 nodes.

The modeling method of one element for per ply of the curved laminate provides a reasonable approximation of the through-thickness stresses. The modeling method of one element for per one degree sweeping around the curved region, that is to say that there are totally 90 elements distributed along the circumstantial direction in the 90 degree curved region, which provides accurate stress prediction in the circumstantial direction of curved region. There are totally 14 elements along the width direction.

The mesh density and aspect ratio in the contact areas between the fastener and curved laminate will affect the convergence of the simulation results, and the meshes in these areas are more refined than those in other areas. Thirty-two elements are equally distributed on the periphery of the fastener hole along circumferential direction, which is similar to the mesh convergence results of F.Rosales-Iriarte et al.[10] and M.A. McCarthy et al.[11].

The nodes at the end of the leg of the specimen are held fixed in all three translational directions (U_x , U_y and U_z). The symmetry surface of the specimen is constrained in translational direction U_z . The top surface of the fastener is declared as a rigid body and has pin relationship with a reference node. Thus, the motion of the top surface is governed by the motion of the reference node, which is held fixed in two translational directions (U_x and U_z) and three rotational directions (R_x , R_y and R_z), while a pull load is applied along U_y direction.

Since the only failure mode of the specimens is delamination between the layers of the curved laminates, three-dimensional Ye delamination criteria[12] is applied in the finite element model to predict the failure of the specimens, which is illustrated as in Equation (1) and (2).

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{33}}{S_{33}^T}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{13}}{S_{13}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{23}}{S_{23}}\right)^2 \geq 1, \sigma_{33} \geq 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{33}}{S_{33}^C}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{13}}{S_{13}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{23}}{S_{23}}\right)^2 \geq 1, \sigma_{33} < 0 \quad (2)$$

Fig. 5 Finite element model of Fabric-1 subjected to tensile load

4 Results analysis and discussion

4.1 Load-displacement curves

According to the four kinds of specimen numerical analysis results, the curves of Load versus displacement are drawn in Fig.6. Compared with the test results which shown in Fig.4, a good agreement both in stiffness and strength of the four different kinds of specimens can be found, considering the imperfection of specimens during the manufacture process and the dispersion of the tests. Therefore the simulated method is validated.

Fig.6 The load-displacement curves of simulation results

4.2 Stress distribution

After the finite element method was validated to be true, further studies can be carried out according to the simulation results. To study the stress distribution of the curved laminate, a cylindrical coordinate system had been created as shown in Fig.7. R_i is the inner radius and R_o is the outer radius of the curved laminate, t is the thickness of the laminate. Each point in the curved region can be defined by R and θ in the cylindrical coordinate system. A path include the maximum stress location along the circumferential direction which was named path-1 and another path include the maximum stress location along the thickness direction which was named path-2 were created. Both the σ_{33} and σ_{13} distribution along the circumferential direction and the thickness direction were analyzed in this paper.

Fig.7 Notation of the location in the angle region

1) Stress along the circumferential direction

Figures 8 and 9 illustrate the calculation results of the radial and tangential stress along the circumferential direction, respectively. As shown in Fig.8, the radial stress distribution of the four different kinds of specimen along the circumferential direction in path-1 shared the same trend, and almost the same values. With the increase of the θ , the σ_{33} increases at first and reaches to its summit at about 30° , and the σ_{33} almost keeps a constant value between 20° and 30° , finally the stress quickly decreased when θ is bigger than 80° .

Form the Fig.9, it can be seen that the tangential stress σ_{13} increases all the time from negative value to positive value as the angle increases, and the values of σ_{13} are about 25MPa at the end the curved angle, which is most close to the loading arm. It can

also be found that when the radial stress σ_{33} reach the maximum value, the tangential stress σ_{13} has a value about zero at an angle $\theta = 30^\circ$.

Fig.8 The σ_{33} along the circumferential direction

Fig.9 The σ_{13} along the circumferential direction

2) Stress along the thickness direction

Figures 10 and 11 illustrate the calculation results of the radial and tangential stress along the thickness direction respectively. The radial stress distribution of the four different kinds of specimen in path-2 shared the same trend. The σ_{33} of the Fabric-1 reaches to its summit at the second layer of nodes, that is to say between the second and third second layers of elements. The σ_{33} of the Fabric-2, Fabric-3 and Fabric-4 reach to their summit at the third layer of nodes, that is to say between the third and fourth layers of elements. The ply angles of these two layers of elements are (0,90) and (± 45), respectively. From Fig.10, it can also be seen that the σ_{33} increase abruptly at the ninth layer of nodes

for Fabric-1, at eleventh layers of nodes for Fabric-2, at twelfth layers nodes for Fabric-3, and at both thirteenth and fifteenth layers of nodes for Fabric-4. And those nodes are also at the interface between the (0,90) and (± 45) layers of elements. This means that the σ_{33} will increase a lot the ply angles of the adjacent layers are different. While the thicknesses are different between the four groups of specimens, the maximum radial stress was almost the same according to the simulation results, as shown in Fig.10.

From Fig.11, it can be seen that the tangential stress along the thickness direction was approximately an order of magnitude smaller than the radial stress. Although the tangential stress has different value in different laminate layer, it has less important influence on the failure of the curved laminate structure.

Fig.10 The σ_{33} along the thickness direction

Fig.11 The σ_{13} along the thickness direction

5 Conclusions

In this paper, the failure process of curved woven fabric laminates with variable thickness is studied experimentally and numerically. Delamination is the only failure mode found in the four different groups of specimen with different laminate thicknesses and stacking sequences, and the failure location is close to the inner surface of the curved laminate. The curved woven fabric laminates fail unstably. The simulation results discover the character of the stress distributions in the curved region and the exact location of the failure onset.

References

- [1] LEKHNITSKII, S.G. “*Anisotropic Plates*”, 3rd edition, Gordon and Breach Science Publishers, New York, 1984.
- [2] K. Lin and C. Hsieh. “Finite deformation of 2-D laminated curved beams with variable curvatures”. *International Journal of Non-Linear Mechanics*, Vol. 46, pp 1293-1304, 2011.
- [3] LIN K-C, HSIEH C-M. “The closed form general solutions of 2-D curved laminated beams of variable curvatures”. *Composite Structures*, Vol 79, 4, pp 606-618, 2007.
- [4] W. Cui. “Interlaminar tensile strength measurement of woven glass/polyester laminates using four-point curved beam specimen”. *Composites Part A*, Vol. 27, pp 1097-1105, 1995.
- [5] ASTM D 6415/D 6415M-06, “Standard test method for measuring the curved beam strength of a fiber-reinforced polymer-matrix composite”. *American society for testing and materials*, 2007.
- [6] R. Martin. “Delamination failure in a unidirectional curved composite laminate”. NASA CR 182018, April 1990.
- [7] R. Martin and W. Jackson. “Damage prediction in cross-ply curved composite laminates”. NASA TM 104089, July 1991.
- [8] JOH D. “A semi-micromechanic interlaminar strain analysis on curved-beam specimens”. NASA Contactor report-NASA CR 189512. 1990.
- [9] ABAQUS documentation, version 6.9.
- [10] Rosales-Iriarte F., Fellows N.A. Durodola J.F. “Failure prediction in carbon compression subjected to bearing versus bypass loading”. *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol.46, 15, pp 1859-1878, 2012.
- [11] Padhi G.S., McCarthy M.A., McCarthy C.T. “BOLJAT: a tool for designing composite bolted joints using three-dimensional finite element analysis”. *Composites: Part A*, Vol.33, pp 1573–1584, 2002.
- [12] Ye L. “Role of matrix resin in delamination onset and growth in composite laminates”. *Composite science and technology*, Vol.33, pp 257-277, 1988.